

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPLICATIONS IN CHILDREN FROM THE ENT ORGANS AFTER AN ACUTE RESPIRATORY VIRAL INFECTION

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Abstract

Acute Respiratory Viral Infection (ARVI) is a serious public health problem due to its high prevalence in both children and adults. These are the most frequent diseases in outpatient practice, more than 80% of all calls to family doctors and pediatricians are caused by ARVI. The highest incidence rate was noted in young children. It is in this age category that the course of ARVI is characterized by the development of severe syndromes and bacterial complications that determine the severity and outcome of the disease. Sufferers of ARVI usually do not leave behind long-term stable immunity, and the lack of acquired immunity and a large number of serotypes of ARVI pathogens can contribute to the development of several episodes of the disease during the year in the same patients. In most cases, respiratory viruses cause an acute respiratory viral disease, which proceeds in the usual form, but in some patients, especially young children, it is accompanied by complications from the bronchopulmonary system and ENT organs in the form of bronchitis, bronchiolitis, otitis, rhinosinusitis and others.

Keywords: *Acute Respiratory Viral Infection, ENT diseases, complications, children*

At the first stage of life, protection against most viruses and bacteria is provided by mother's milk, but in the future, the child has to develop its own protective barrier, the creation of which is both hindered and facilitated by internal factors, anatomical and hormonal features of the body, and the external environment. So, for example, periodic overheating or hypothermia can lead to a weakening of the child's body's resistance to infections, which will primarily affect the ENT organs. Children are much more likely to suffer from diseases of the ENT organs compared to older people. This is due to unformed immunity, increased secretion of glands, narrow nasal passages and other anatomical and physiological features.

Chronic ENT diseases can lead to serious health problems. In order to protect your child from ear-throat-nose diseases and their consequences, it is necessary, first of all, to understand the variety and danger of such diseases.

The most frequent causes of diseases of the ENT organs:

- infectious agents (measles, diphtheria, flu);
- environmental factors (cold wind, downpour, dry air);
- injuries, foreign bodies;
- fungal infection of the ear cavity;
- decrease in immunity against the background of exacerbation of chronic pathology, vitamin deficiency;
- changes in the microflora of the nasopharynx (activation of streptococci);
- tumor process;
- frequent allergies;
- incorrect intake of some medicines.

In ENT diseases in childhood, the symptoms are more often bright and with a pronounced pain syndrome than in adults. Parents are usually scared and try to suppress them as soon as possible with improvised, often folk, means, while you should immediately consult a doctor.

As soon as the ARVI and flu season arrives, the respiratory tracts lined from the inside with epithelium, the main task of which is to delay the entry of viruses and bacteria into the body, are usually the first to suffer from a viral infection. But "insidious" microorganisms against the background of violation of the protective barriers of the nasopharynx, a decrease in non-specific and specific anti-infective immunity, under the influence of hypothermia, neuropsychological overstrain and adverse environmental influences, still get into the cells of the upper respiratory tract, multiply in them and cause diseases. Protective barriers and immunity are imperfect in children, so they get sick more often.

Children of the first year, especially in the first 6 months of life, are a high-risk group for the adverse course of respiratory tract infections. A child of this age is characterized by:

- physiological morphofunctional immaturity of the respiratory tract and immune system;
- unstable microbiosis of the mucous membranes of the upper respiratory tract, which in adults is a powerful natural anti-infective barrier.

Anatomical and functional features of the respiratory system in children create prerequisites for easier breathing disorders than in adults. The most frequent causative agents of acute respiratory infections with damage to the lower respiratory tract are influenza, parainfluenza, and respiratory syncytial virus. The upper parts are more often affected by coronaviruses, ad-

enoviruses and entero- and rhinoviruses, herpes simplex viruses type 1 (HPV-1), Epstein-Barr virus, although their role in the damage of the lower parts of the respiratory tract cannot be completely excluded. Adenovirus infection, in addition to respiratory manifestations, is accompanied by conjunctivitis.

Other reasons for the development of GRI are viral-bacterial associations, bacteria, fungi, protozoa. The viral-bacterial and bacterial nature of respiratory diseases is more characteristic of newborns, infants and

young children. Viral and bacterial lesions are associated with the activation of microbial autoflora in connection with a violation of the barrier function of the respiratory tract and a decrease in the body's protective properties, as well as superinfection with bacterial agents. The addition of a bacterial infection leads to an increase in the severity of the disease and may be the main cause of an adverse outcome.

At the same time, there are primary bacterial infections of the respiratory tract (Table 1).

Table 1

Clinical syndromes of ARI of bacterial etiology

Causative bacteria	Main syndromes
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	Otitis, sinusitis, pneumonia, conjunctivitis
<i>Haemophilus influenzae capsular</i>	Epiglottitis, pneumonia
<i>Haemophilus influenzae capsuleless</i>	Sinusitis, otitis, conjunctivitis
<i>Moraxella catarrhalis</i>	Otitis, sinusitis (mainly in children who previously received antibiotics)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Otitis, purulent sinusitis, pneumonia
<i>Mycoplasma pneumoniae</i>	Nasopharyngitis, bronchitis, conjunctivitis
<i>Chlamydomphila pneumoniae</i>	Pharyngitis, tonsillitis, lymphadenitis, bronchitis
<i>Chlamydomphila trachomatis</i>	Conjunctivitis, bronchitis, pneumonia in children 0–6 months.

According to statistics, more than 50% of all appeals to children's polyclinics are related to diseases of the ENT organs. It is at an early age that these diseases pass with the greatest complications, so it is necessary to diagnose and treat them in time.

Children often develop acute ENT diseases, which are characterized by a violent onset, high intoxication of the body and a rapid course. A viral infection depletes the immune system, and the disease is often accompanied by complications of a bacterial nature. The risk of such complications is highest in the absence of timely and comprehensive treatment and in patients with chronic inflammatory diseases of the upper respiratory tract, nasal sinuses, oral cavity, etc. Among them are bronchitis, pneumonia, sinusitis, otitis, pyelonephritis, meningitis, heart failure and others. Some complications are asymptomatic, but as a result immunity decreases, the risk of cancer increases, and old age comes earlier.

Classic flu and acute respiratory infections pass, as a rule, in 4-10 days. If the baby is sick longer, this is a reason to think about the prevention of complications. In this case, a thorough diagnosis and additional treatment, which is different from the treatment of ARI and flu, is necessary.

Among the main complications after the flu in children, the following should be highlighted:

1. Bronchitis and pneumonia.

Let's immediately note that a viral infection often immediately causes bronchitis or pneumonia. It is not a complication or secondary infection. Symptoms of the disease appear immediately and subside as treatment progresses. But if after several days of therapy there is a sharp deterioration of the condition, additional symptoms appear, you can think about the addition of a secondary infection. The following symptoms deserve special attention (let's be clear right away, the child's symptoms and complaints are not the same thing):

Cough. Pay attention to its intensity (became more frequent or stronger), time and situations that aggravate

the cough (in the morning, in a lying position, when getting out of bed).

High humidity. It will be important for your doctor to know whether sputum comes out when you cough, what color it is (transparent mucous or purulent - yellowish-green), how easily it is coughed up.

Pay attention to the complaint of chest pain (sometimes the child can even show the place where it hurts).

Difficulty breathing and connection with inhalation and exhalation.

Temperature. If the temperature rises, pay attention to what time of day it is.

Increased sweating.

You should inform your doctor about any change in the child's condition, who can add antibacterial drugs, expectorants and antitussives to the treatment.

2. Sinusitis

This term is called inflammation of the paranasal sinuses. In total, a person has four groups of sinuses. Most often, inflammation of the maxillary sinuses (sinusitis) and frontal sinuses (frontitis) develops. Normally, additional sinuses are filled with air. Infectious rhinitis causes swelling of the mucous membrane that lines the nasal passages. This disrupts the connection between the sinus cavity and the nose and makes the sinus a closed space, ideal for bacterial growth. The beginning of sinusitis is manifested by the appearance of pain on both sides of the nose. Due to the fact that the maxillary and frontal additional sinuses are connected by passages, a few days after the onset of sinusitis, frontitis can develop, manifested by pain in the forehead. The diagnosis is made on the basis of an examination (at an ENT doctor) and an X-ray. Antibacterial drugs, vasoconstrictors (it is important to ensure the outflow of secretions from the inflamed sinus), physiotherapy (warming up, inhalations) are added to the treatment.

3. Otitis

Young children - under the age of 3 are especially prone to otitis. According to statistics, 80% of children at this age suffered at least one episode of otitis media.

This is due to the peculiarity of the structure of the auditory tube - it is shorter than in adults, which makes it more vulnerable to inflammatory processes. Otitis begins with a feeling of congestion and noise in the ear. And then it is difficult not to notice the symptoms of otitis - there is a sharp shooting pain in the ear, which can be so strong that the child loses sleep and appetite. The pain is in the teeth, in the neck, in the eye, and the temperature rises. Self-medication for otitis is dangerous, therefore, if pain occurs in the ear, you should immediately consult a doctor.

The list of complications after ARVI and influenza in children is quite long, and diseases often caused by ARVI can pose a greater danger to frail children's health than the flu itself.

How to avoid complications after ARVI in children - strike at the root cause

The main reason for the development of complications is insufficient work of the immune system. The protective system weakens, throwing all its forces to destroy viruses. In addition, viruses have a harmful effect on cells and disrupt the permeability of capillaries. The latter opens additional gates for infection (it is even easier than before to get into cells). Therefore, during the treatment of viral respiratory diseases, agents for strengthening immunity are often prescribed. They affect the root cause - they destroy the virus and strengthen the body's immune response.

Prevention of complications:

In order to prevent ENT disease in children, it is necessary to take the following preventive measures aimed at increasing immunity and reducing the likelihood of infection:

- limiting contacts with patients;
- systematic hardening (without supercooling);
- maintenance of normal air humidity in the room;
- ventilation of premises (without drafts);
- inclusion of fresh vegetables and fruits in the diet;
- taking vitamins.
- vaccination is one of the ways to prevent the disease, and accordingly to avoid complications (3).
- consulting a doctor within 48 hours after the first signs of the disease appear.
- fulfillment of all doctor's appointments.

It is very important to constantly monitor the child's health in order to avoid dangerous conditions.

You should contact the ENT if you have the following symptoms:

- ✓ dry or wet cough;
- ✓ sore throat, difficulty swallowing;
- ✓ chronic infection of the nasopharynx (pharyngitis, tonsillitis, tonsillitis, adenoids);
- ✓ runny nose, chronic nasal congestion;
- ✓ violation of breathing through the nose (for example, an open mouth in a dream, or snoring);

- ✓ pain in the ears;
- ✓ frequent colds in the child.

These symptoms can be a signal of the beginning of otitis, sore throat and cold.

Any disturbance in the functioning of the respiratory or hearing organs in a child is also a signal that you need a consultation with an ENT doctor.

Despite the fact that ENT diseases are difficult for children to tolerate, treatment always arouses their curiosity. In the therapy of ENT diseases, various devices and devices are used, the type and device of which distract the child from negative emotions.

Conclusions. The dependence of the clinical course of otorhinolaryngological diseases on age-related anatomical and physiological features is most pronounced in newborns and infants, which constantly requires the qualified supervision of an otorhinolaryngologist. There are a number of diseases that are characteristic only of this age, and which occur less often as the child grows and develops.

The basis of the prevention of otorhinolaryngological diseases and their complications should be considered the examination of newborns and infants with the participation of an otorhinolaryngologist who has a clear idea of the age-related features of the course of diseases of the ENT organs.

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